

Effect of propanediol on chemical speciation of phenanthroline complexes of toxic metals

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Abstract : The stability of the binary complexes of toxic metal ions such as Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with 1,10-phenanthroline is studied by pH metry in (0.0–60.0% v/v) 1,2-propanediol-water mixtures at 303 K and 0.16 mol L⁻¹ ionic strength. The trend in β values of the metal-ligand complexes with the dielectric constant is explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

Keywords : Toxic metal ions, 1,10-phenanthroline, binary complexes, 1,2-propanediol.

Introduction

The aim of present study is to obtain quantitative information on the complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with Phen as binary metal complexes in aqueous mixture of 1,2-propanediol, also known as propylene glycol (PG). PG-water mixtures are expected to mimic the polarity of biofluids where the concept of equivalent solution dielectric constant¹ for protein cavities is applicable.

Results and discussion

The linear variation of stability constants (Table 1) of Phen complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with reciprocal of dielectric constant (1/D) of PG-water mixture indicates the dominance² of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces under the present experimental conditions.

The distribution diagrams obtained from DISPLOT³ (Fig. 1) show that the dissociation of the proton associated with nitrogen takes place in the pH range 2.0–6.0. Since LH⁺ is the predominant form of the ligand in the present experimental conditions, there is no scope for the formation of protonated metal complexes in this study. The best fit model contains mononuclear, unprotonated, unhydroxylated species, viz. ML²⁺ and ML₂²⁺ in the case of Pb^{II} and ML²⁺, ML₂²⁺ and ML₃²⁺ for Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} (Table 1). The formation of these species could be

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Phen complexes with Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} in PG-water mixtures

% v/v PG	log β_{mth} (SD)		
	110	120	130
	Pb ^{II}		
0.0	3.65(25)	7.18(25)	
10.0	3.12(21)	6.17(37)	
20.0	3.02(30)	6.04(32)	
30.0	3.09(16)	6.10(11)	
40.0	3.40(12)	6.47(10)	
50.0	3.58(10)	6.79(22)	
60.0	3.12(25)	6.55(8)	
	Cd ^{II}		
0.0	5.42(15)	9.47(20)	13.26(21)
10.0	5.81(14)	9.80(21)	13.85(15)
20.0	5.57(14)	9.95(26)	14.18(26)
30.0	5.87(14)	10.29(24)	14.12(18)
40.0	5.33(12)	10.09(7)	13.16(18)
50.0	5.42(28)	9.88(18)	13.11(26)
60.0	5.65(11)	9.65(8)	12.81(14)
	Hg ^{II}		
0.0	6.20(32)	12.20(20)	15.01(26)
10.0	6.82(13)	13.51(12)	16.05(26)
20.0	6.29(23)	13.21(25)	16.08(28)
30.0	6.59(89)	12.91(67)	16.31(72)
40.0	5.99(28)	11.98(24)	16.04(20)
50.0	6.44(10)	12.46(12)	15.91(24)
60.0	5.83(12)	11.81(8)	15.37(15)

Fig. 1. Distribution diagrams of Phen complexes in 30% v/v PG-water mixture; (A) Pb^{II}, (B) Cd^{II} and (C) Hg^{II}. FM = Free metal ion and FL = Free ligand.

described according to the following equilibria :

The pattern of distribution of species with pH (Fig. 1) shows that the concentration of ML^{2+} increases and then decreases, whereas the concentration of ML_2^{2+} increases in the case of Pb^{II}. It is observed that the concentrations of ML^{2+} and ML_2^{2+} species increase and then decrease in the case of Cd^{II}. The concentration of ML^{2+} is less than or equal to 10% at all pH range of study and ML_2^{2+} decreases in the case of Hg^{II}. In the case of Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} the concentration of ML_3^{2+} species increases, whereas ML_3^{2+} is not detected in the case of Pb^{II}. The latter is probably due to the small ionic radius⁴ of Pb^{II} which cannot accommodate three molecules of Phen. Another notable observation is that the free metal ion concentration is in the order : Pb^{II} > Cd^{II} > Hg^{II}, indicating the increasing stability of the metal complexes in the order : Hg^{II} > Cd^{II} > Pb^{II}. Simultaneous formation of ML_2^{2+} and ML_3^{2+} in Fig. 1B can be explained by the simultaneous existence of eqs. (2) and (3).

The Phen complexes of these metal ions are more stable in PG-water mixtures than in urea-water mixtures⁴, because urea is a coordinating molecule which competes with ligand for the metal site.

Materials and methods :

A 0.05 mol L⁻¹ Phen (Merck, India) solution was prepared in triple distilled water. 0.1 mol L⁻¹ Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} nitrates and 0.05 mol L⁻¹ Hg^{II} nitrate aqueous solutions were prepared in triple distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid, to suppress the hydrolysis of the metal salts. Sodium nitrate was used to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. 0.4 mol L⁻¹ Sodium hydroxide and 0.2 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid solutions were prepared in triple distilled water. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. The strengths of alkali and acid were determined using the Gran plot method⁵. The errors in the determination of concentrations of ligand, metal ions, acid and alkali were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA)⁶.

Procedure :

All the pH metric titrations were carried out at 303 K in a medium containing varying concentrations of the PG-water mixtures (0.0-60.0% v/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium nitrate. The measurements were recorded with a calibrated ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter. The glass electrode was equilibrated

in a well stirred PG-water mixture containing inert electrolyte. Titration of strong acid with alkali was carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved or not. Then the calomel electrode was refilled with PG-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 mL. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.5 and 1 : 5) of metal to ligand were performed with 0.40 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere⁷.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD⁸ was used to calculate the correction factor. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least squares analysis program MINQUAD75⁹ which exploits the advantage of constrained least squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of undamped, unconstrained Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of the binary systems, the correction factor and the protonation constant of Phen were fixed. The

variation of stability constants with the dielectric constant of the medium was analyzed on electrostatic grounds based on solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

References

1. H. Sigel, R. B. Martin, R. Tribolet, U. K. Haring and R. M. Balakrishnan, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1985, **152**, 187.
2. M. S. Babu, G. N. Rao, K. V. Ramana and M. S. P. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 38.
3. G. N. Rao, A. R. Babu, S. V. V. S. Rao, R. S. Rao and K. V. Ramana, *Acta Cien. Indica*, 1989, **15**, 321.
4. N. Padmaja, M. S. Babu, G. N. Rao, R. S. Rao and K. V. Ramana, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 2497.
5. G. Gran, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **206**, 111.
6. R. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, "Computer Applications in Chemistry", Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai, 2005, 302.
7. M. P. Latha, V. M. Rao, T. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop.*, 2007, **21**, 363.
8. G. N. Rao, PhD Thesis, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India, 1989.
9. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.

